

1898, 1899-1907 and 1908-1914 frames, will be used in this regard to temporally dynamize my analysis. Fourthly, within each snapshot itself I will address the level of cohesion based on Thierry Rossier's (2022) typology of Swiss elites in the interwar period.

This paper is not only innovative as it addresses the often-overlooked non-Western Egyptian elite, but even more so through its attention for external influences on elite formation as well as by bringing in a spatial dimension. In the first place, I will assess the impact of the presence of the foreign diplomatic corps in Egypt on organisational clustering in the elite communities. Often presented as the ultimate gateway to social promotion, I will challenge the assumption that consular offices had this function per se. Instead, this paper will position diplomatic office-holding members of the local Egyptian elite in a more sophisticated social structure. Secondly, I will assess the relation between the foreign diplomatic corps and the presence of both career diplomats and locally recruited agents on the one hand and the patchwork of judicial, socio-cultural, economic, and learned organisations on the other. I argue that against the backdrop of an increasing professionalization of the diplomatic corps, the Levantine and foreign local elites that had formerly been in foreign service, organised their local and international contacts in a plethora of other organisations. Making use of the K-core decomposition method (Seidman 1983; Kong, Shi, Whu and Zhang, 2022), this evolution, the tightness of these new networks, and the relative role of particular sectors and their organisations will be scrutinized. In sum, I will thus provide an innovative and quantitatively-underpinned understanding of the formation of elites in late-nineteenth century Egypt that surpasses the much-fragmented historiography and overcomes many of the bureaucratic and practical hurdles related to doing archival research in contemporary Egypt (Carminati 2018).

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